

THE QUESTION OF PRINCIPALITIES IN THE PROCESSES OF
PARTICIPATION OF INDIA AND PAKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the fate of semi-independent principalities (states) in the subcontinent and their geopolitical choices during the division of British India into two independent states in 1947. The study analyzes the freedom of legal choice granted to the rulers of the principalities against the backdrop of the retreat of the British Empire, the conditions for joining the dominions of India and Pakistan, and the diplomatic and military struggles in this process. In particular, the annexation crises of large and strategically important principalities such as Kashmir, Hyderabad, and Junagadh are revealed, along with their long-term systemic impact on the modern South Asian security architecture and the escalation of India-Pakistan relations.

Keywords: *India, Pakistan, partition (1947), princely question, subcontinent, Kashmir crisis, Hyderabad, Junagadh, Mountbatten plan, dominion, sovereignty, South Asian geopolitics, territorial conflict.*

Introduction. In understanding the problems of post-independence relations between India and Pakistan, it is advisable to focus on the activities of the principalities in British India on the eve of independence and the attitude of the missions sent by London, as well as the Congress and the Muslim League towards them. Although the issue of principalities was not initially given sufficient attention, it became a pressing political issue on the eve of independence. Most of the principalities sought to adapt to the new political system and join while retaining certain privileges. During this period, the Congress also pursued a cautious policy toward the principalities, attempting their gradual integration.

By 1946, the Plan of the Ministerial Mission provided for the allocation of important seats to princes in the Constituent Assembly and the preservation of their political role during the transition period. However, the political process was complicated by the opposition of the Muslim League and certain other forces. The House of Princes initially refused to participate in the Constituent Assembly, but later partially joined, indicating their internal division.

Some representatives of the colonial administration, including political advisor K. Corfield, supported a conservative approach toward the principalities and advocated for the preservation of their independent status. This approach was seen as

an alternative political option for some principalities on their way to independence. Later, during the reign of Viceroy Mountbatten, this issue was also discussed, and various proposals were put forward to preserve or reform the territorial structure of India.

A commission headed by S. Redcliffe was established to carry out the territorial division. His decision was announced after independence, and the provinces of Punjab and Bengal were divided mainly on the basis of religious demographic composition, and in some cases additional factors were taken into account.

As a result of the division, a geographically disconnected state structure was formed, consisting of the western and eastern parts of Pakistan. The western part included, in addition to the Punjab, Sindh, the North-West Frontier Province, and Baluchistan, while the eastern part consisted of the Muslim-populated part of Bengal. The final formation of the two dominions also depended on the decisions of the rulers of the Indian principalities, whose territory and population played an important role in the overall indicators.

The Mountbatten community, itself, and the London government formed a clear position on the question of the principalities after the adoption of the partition plan by Congress. At the same time, British policy was aimed at maintaining the special status of the principalities and preventing the transfer of their sovereignty to new dominions.

The approach to the issue of principalities reflected the difference between conservative and liberal political views. Considering the need for a broad political consensus on this matter, the government of Attlee specifically noted the princely states in the Indian Independence Act of July 18, 1947. It established the termination of the crown's sovereignty over the principalities and the restoration of their previously existing rights.

At the same time, the development of the principalities as independent states was not envisaged, and they had the opportunity to join India or Pakistan. Although some rulers tried to maintain independence, such a position was practically complex.

Mountbatten took an active part in negotiations with the principalities, urging them to choose the appropriate dominion, taking into account its geographical location and the interests of its population. By the declaration of independence, most of the principalities had decided in favor of either India or Pakistan. In exceptional cases, certain principalities sought to maintain their independence or special status.

Among the disputed territories were the princely states of Hyderabad, Junagadh, and Jammu and Kashmir. While the ruler of Junagadh expressed a desire to join Pakistan, the population was predominantly Indian. In the princely state of Jammu

and Kashmir, however, the ruler remained in an uncertain position, and a temporary status quo agreement was implemented.

The Kashmir issue remained relevant in subsequent periods and became one of the primary disputed territories between India and Pakistan. The fragmented state of the territory and the disagreements regarding it influenced the political situation in the region.

The role of British policy in shaping the Kashmir issue is assessed differently. Some of Mountbatten's decisions, including the process of establishing territorial boundaries, may have influenced the annexation of the principalities.

At the same time, the British administration was forced to take into account the principle of democratic self-determination in its policy. In some regions, plebiscites were held, and this principle was also applied to the principalities.

The military-political situation in Kashmir has led to an escalation of the conflict between India and Pakistan. Although a common military governance system existed between the two countries during this period, it was later abolished and the issue reached an international level. Furthermore, relations between the two countries were complicated by problems related to the distribution of financial resources, population migration, and the formation of public administration.

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